

Multiculturalism, and Emergence of Vikram Seth as Writer with References to the Status of Women

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Abstract

Vikram Seth is an artist and a storyteller to be reckoned with. He has a gift for storytelling. Seth has a wide range of interests and talents. He has a wide range of emotions. His writing can not be confined to just a few topics. He does an excellent job of weaving together different elements of the plot. Naturally, one component connects to the other. As seen in the writing, the word Patriarchy was around before the current resurgence of the ladies' development and ladies' investigations courses. In the previous twenty years, the idea has been reproduced to break down the beginnings and states of men's persecution of ladies. In A Suitable Boy, Vikram Seth depicts the universe of post-autonomy ladies' condition in detail. His ladies' characters are related to the family bunch.

Keywords: Patriarchy, Post-Independence India, Feminism, Socio-Cultural aspects, Gender Discrimination

I. INTRODUCTION

In human society, each gender plays playing its indispensable role. However, in the society depicted in "A Suitable Boy," a female life is narrowed down to wifehood and later motherhood. He has created impressive pictures of females in different societies of different periods. In Seth's novel "A Suitable Boy," the depiction of patriarchal society and patriarchal values are implanted in the post-independent Indian community. It is seen that poor patriarchal society utilized violence against women as a powerful tool to control women's sexuality. However, the depiction of female characters in Two Lives, The Golden Gate, and An Equal Music" are not strict to a particular modal character. However, it varies with the background of the novels in which it is set [1].

Indian English literature was concerned about the socio-cultural status of pre-independence and post-independence India in social, economic, spiritual, historical, linguistic, government, and individual psyche. Literature is not pure historical documentation but focuses on some specific time representing social values and political norms. This notion of culture is chauvinistic and Eurocentric, providing a scientific rationale for imperialism in suppressing the savage and primordial. The term culture 'has been employed to refer refinement 'or well

being.' Since its commencement of human evolution, culture extensively infused and entrenched into human life. His values, actions, morals, thoughts, and beliefs as well as his everyday conduct are affected by society as the newborn baby joins the world culture less. Though culture is a man made environment it gives meaning to man's life. In this manner, it tends to be accepted that once culture is built up, it has its capacity [2]. Indian fiction in English is the ideal archive sources that uncovered India's culture. Indo-Anglian fiction is a major source for a systematic study of cultural contact and cultural change with the Indian worldview as a focus of the Westerners to increase their knowledge of acculturation processes. Every writer has their own perspective on society and in their works, they depict their impression of history, network, ethnic qualities and human association. Their delineation and depiction of the society performs as a hologram. Novelist's socio-cultural perceptions highlight the ethnicity, social-political status, religion, rituals, arts, growth of literature, status of women, life of the youngsters, education system, technology development, and sexual relationship [3]. During English colonization, India has fifteen major languages and more than seven hundred twenty dialects. English language influenced the fortunate upper class people and the issuing of magazines and journals in English make a great influence on the rise of Indian nationalism and contemporary Indian literature. Indian individuals begin to seek after their degrees in Western nations, they step by step enticed by the remote culture and starts to settle down in outside land. The impact of modernizations acquires huge changes in India and this change in socio-social angles reflects in the Indian English Literature. This literature applies to the works written by the Indian authors who write in English but in fact, their native language might be one of India's many languages [4]. Vikram Seth is one of the most famous Indian Authors in English. With the quality and broadness of his work and his noteworthy accomplishment in both composition and section, Seth has indicated his dominance of English through his utilization of articulation and the narrating strategy of exposition refrains. His subjects were on the Post-Independence India, Western Classical Music and human connections. He is sturdily established in the social-social circumstances of contemporary India. Vikram Seth's novels delineate the post-freedom Indian lifestyle style. He accomplished extraordinary recognition with his refrain writing style and was viewed as one of the main writers of Indian English Literature. His three novels: *A Suitable Child*, *The Golden Gate* and *An Equal Music* depict the cultures and history of the different nations. Thus it allows the reader to get knowledge of the different cultures across the world. His major characters are professionally related to computers, engineering, music, education, politics and commerce. The milieu of the 8 three novels is Silicon Valley of Californian, India after Independence and in London and Vienna. Seth novels pay attention on the stressed relationships and the loss of faith in human values. The domestic life and social life has shrunk both structurally and functionally due to the political system. Vikram Seth is well aware of the events and activities which affected the social harmony of the system. He portrays the picture of the twenty first century modern world in his novels. He additionally centers intensely around sexual connections and common understandings of the darlings, companions and relations. In India, the political circumstance has abandoned great to most exceedingly terrible and however the decree of majority rules system _Government for the individuals, by the individuals and to the individuals' has been actualized in the Indian

constitution it has been barely trailed by the political pursuers. What is more, the statement, —service to individuals is administration to country got purposeless.

II. EMERGENCE OF VIKRAM SETH AS A WRITER

Vikram Seth's rise to prominence as a writer has been widely publicized, with media headlines and pieces praising him. There are no limits to the kind of stories Seth may create. His work is excellent, and it is worth your time to read it, regardless of whether or not you think he gets much money from it. While he has dabbled in other forms of writing, his books have elevated him to a position of incomparable renown. He is a unique writer because of the breadth and depth of his output. Modern Indian English literature has gone beyond national bounds because Seth incorporated literary traditions worldwide [5]. After studying the greatest of the world's cultures, he aims to combine them into his own. India, China, England, and California have all been designated as Seth's quarters. While living in different places, he has integrated their culture into his personality and creativity. As a result of his cultural absorption, he can write literature that transcends the borders of India. In the beginning, Seth was just a regular writer, but his inventiveness propelled him to ever-greater heights until he finally reached the top. A fixation with style and modernist knowledge has driven Seth to abandon the fundamental task of putting words on paper. According to Vikram Seth's own words:

“I don't read lot of modern fiction, but it seems to me that too much of it is a thesis fodder. Since the rise of the academic critic, writing has had to have an increasing sophistication, as if subjects such as love, ambition and family are worthy only at the airport novel. Writers come out of university courses and carry into their writing academic corners rather than the corners of the general reader.” (Gavron, Jeremy April 7)

Seth has a clear idea of what he wants to accomplish as an aspiring artist. To him, it is more important to write about the cultures he encounters than it is to learn about the places he visits. He is aware that this development elevates his work to a new level. If you read Seth's work, you can be sure that the cultures of many places are shown accurately, whether it is a story set in Modern America, Europe, or India. Seth thinks that the characters in a show should reflect the real-life persons they are based on. When he creates a character, he likes to give them the intimidating characteristics of everyday guys. R.K. Narayan, who admires Seth's writing, says this:

“I realized, here was a genuine writer with the right values, gift and outlook, not writing in order to blow off steam or to reform society but a genuine artist who takes pleasure in writing.” (Interview with India Today)

As a breath of fresh air compared to the suffocating prose of his contemporaries, his writing is like a breath of fresh air. His ability to combine poetry and ordinary language uniquely makes his work remarkable. As a poet, he first made his mark in the literary community. Seth's *A Suitable Boy* is not necessarily his first novel. However, *The Golden Gate* is a significant moment in Seth's literary career because it gave him the confidence to continue writing novels. Although *The Humble Administrator's Garden* may be considered one of the most significant

English collections of poetry by an Indian, it is the book that brought him to the notice of the reading public. A star has been born in the literary sky, as *The Golden Gate* testifies for Seth. His writing style makes it impossible to label him as a craftsman. In the words of Seth, it serves as a bridge bridging poetry and prose [5]:

*"I didn't know I was a novelist until I wrote *The Golden Gate*." (Writers on Writing Radio Series Transcript).*

Using sonnet form, *The Golden Gate* tells a tale about Silicon Valley's popular culture, focusing on the area's large concentration of computer experts. *All You Who Sleep Tonight*, *Beastly Tales from Here and There*, and *Three Chinese Poets* were the following three poetry books Seth released after *The Golden Gate*. The first and last are on Seth's ties to the United States, China, and India, respectively, and reveal signs of maturity in him. Seth's themes of love, friendship, remembrance, detachment, exile, and loneliness in a distant nation are explored in *All You Who Sleep Tonight*. Seth's work took on a new direction with this book, in which he put his feelings into words. However, Seth's following literary effort, *A Suitable Boy* [6], astonished his international audience. This work's enormous popularity allowed him to shift from poet to novelist with apparent ease and grace. *A Suitable Boy* is a sprawling tale of four families, their friends, neighbors, acquaintances, servants, lovers, and assorted others in the newly independent India in the 1950s. Prerana Sinha adds her perspective:

*"Seth's actual popularity came through his magnum opus *A Suitable Boy*, based on India in 1950s...the novel made him a star in the literary firmament. It was an outright success. It made a history of its kind, just as the author had made in his prolific career. however, this intense author had to face lots of difficulties especially with his had which for some time had refused to function along with his laptop and printer which true to its nature would often not behave properly. Moreover he had greatest difficulty with the foreign publishers who were dependent on Penguin India's typesetting and film and the unavoidable delay that was becoming difficult to control from India." (Vikram Seth: *The Suitable Writer* 23)*

Indian life in post-independence India is the subject of Tolstoy's literary epic *A Suitable Boy*. Megabook is a piece of art in its own right, and it is impossible to fit it in a suitable place. Seth is "a prose writer of enormous power and vision, a novelist of quality and devotion equipped with a talent to sweep the great heritage of the book in English into his vast perspective," and this is a demonstration of his ability [7] A sociological fable about India's many cultures, it is, in fact, an Austenian tale of love and marriage. According to the book's title, the story's focus is a mother's hunt for a "suitable guy" for her daughter. Additionally, it discusses the ramifications of religious strife and the 1947 India-Pakistan split. The novel's action takes place in 1951-52 and depicts India's post-independence political and social life. Seth was born in this particular year.

In the same way, a banyan tree has countless roots and branches, and *A Suitable Boy* is a massive book. In Seth's estimation, this book took six years to write and three to recuperate

from it. (Rediff.com interview) After this book, the only thing he wrote was the libretto for an opera, which makes sense given his prolific output before and after. In 1993, Seth won the Irish Times International Fiction Prize, the Commonwealth Writers Prize, and the W.H. Smith Literary Award for his work on this book. Vikram Seth can blend many cultural contacts throughout his work as a writer. *A Suitable Boy*, his mega-book, is rooted in Indian culture, whereas *An Equal Music*, his most recent work, is rooted in European culture.

In this manner, Seth has managed to write three books about three separate nations and civilizations. The fact that the world belongs to him and his brilliance belongs to the world is a characteristic of his genius. Though Vikram Seth's writings are genuinely Indian, the intellectual and creative environment he has drawn from is essentially international, as a vast number of nineteenth-century Indian authors in English. An old technique of storytelling that goes back to 200 BC is seen in Vikram Seth's collection of animal tales called *Beastly Tales from Here and There*. In our land, the Panchatantra stories were first written down. One fascinating fact about these stories is that they have profoundly impacted both Asian and European folklore. For children and adults alike, his animal tales have an inexplicable appeal. Characters recognizable to the audience are usually amusing, witty, and wacky. There are two stories from India, two from China, two each from Greece, Ukraine, and the 'Land of Gup' - the author's imagination - among the ten monster tales that make up this collection. That Vikram Seth is a poet who can put on the most outlandish and queer outfits without losing his poetic brilliance is well shown by this passage. It is safe to say that the works above of various genres show that Vikram Seth is an accomplished author who is now recognized as one of the best in his field. He discussed various writing styles and genres [8].

A. Patriarchy

Male dominance in political leadership positions, moral authority, social privilege, and property ownership is characteristic of patriarchy, a social structure in which men wield the majority of power and privilege. Fathers and father figures have control over women and children in the household. Property and titles may be passed down in patriarchal civilizations via the male bloodline. Patriarchy has been reflected in various societies' social, legal, political, and economic structures throughout history. Even though their constitutions and laws do not identify patriarchy, almost all nations today are patriarchal. [9].

'THE GOLDEN GATE' AND REALISTIC CONDITION OF FEMALES IN ITS WORLD IN SILICON VALLEY

In America, with a profound change in timings due to scientific innovations status of females also changes as a result of broad spread education. There is economic Independence of females. In "The Golden Gate," the female is purported to enjoy equal status, and there is no economic need for marriage. Instead, there is an emotional need for marriage. So, both males and females enjoy their bachelorhood and even pre-marital sex for physical and mental satisfaction. "The Golden Gate" replicates the same American IT culture [10].

'A SUITABLE BOY' AND INDIAN FEMALES POST-INDEPENDENT ERA

Vikram Seth tries to depict and unveil females with modifications of place and time. After the Indian Constitution was created, the British Constitution's replica of the Magna Carta gave a fundamental right of equality. Even before Independence, women took part in various reforms and rallies and had played an appreciated role. Everybody wanted a perfect wife in an ideal home. Lata is the female lead character of Vikram Seth's novel "A Suitable Boy" and a depiction of the ever-expanding generation gap in post-Independent India. While doing graduation from college. She fell in love with a Muslim boy Kabir Durrani. This love episode points towards an ever-expanding cultural lag. To put it simply, Lata had a hard time getting ready for her pre-arranged marriage. Due to India's importance in agricultural operations, Indians prefer males as heirs to the family farm. They may continue living with their parents after marriage and provide for them as they age.

In contrast, a girl drains family resources, especially when a large dowry goes with her to her husband. This sort of mentality prevails in Indian society, and with the change in time and place, this cultural pattern varies by following natural, cultural patterns. However, later, she changed her mind. Love, passion, and sexual power appear to be sacrifices necessitated by the compulsions of everyday existence. This is how Seth justifies the decision of Lata to marry a man other than her lover.

Lata had alternated between serene optimism And terrifying attacks of uncertainty for the last Week. After the civil ceremony, she felt calm and almost happy, more fond of Haresh than before. He had smiled at her from time to time as if he knew most needed reassurance. (Boy.1335-1336)

AN EQUAL MUSIC AND FEMALE RIGHTS TO LIVE A HAPPY LIFE

In "An Equal Music," the writer has sculpted Julia, a modern female musician, and her love story with a guy and their split. When her lover left her, the writer justifies this character by providing her with a husband after her split with her lover; neither the writer nor her lover criticized her that quick decision even Seth justified her action. So, one can say that Seth always depicts female characters in great originality without adding false colors.

I had slept with another woman before, and she Had had a boyfriend before once, but I was her First love, and she was mine. Nor have I ever been In love since. But then I have never fallen out of love with her- with her, (Music.83)

While writing a novel, Seth creates a character not just from an Indian point of view but from a rational viewpoint. Her lover never criticized Julia for her decision regarding marriage and her separation from her husband; she indulges in an affair with her ex-boyfriend, and writers switch an erotic scene between them.

The sun falls on our bodies. She does not want the blind draws. I run my hands through her hair, So much longer than it used to be. We make love not with tenderness but with ecstasy born of starvation... yet I sense a tension drop away in her. She does not want me to speak, nor does she speak

Herself... the scent of her body, mixed with her faint perfume, drives me into a frenzy. (Music.137)

ORIGINAL CONDITION OF FEMALES IN NAZI GERMANY AND ITS COMPARISON TO 'TWO LIVES'

From 1933 through 1945, Jews and female doctors were prohibited from practicing medicine in Germany under Hitler's dictatorship. When Adolf Hitler was Germany's chancellor during the Third Reich, the country was rife with violence and intolerance. Henny, portrayed as the heroine of "Two Lives," was a prominent victim of Nazi riots. Moreover, her family members, especially her mother and sister, suffered greatly. Moreover, she married an Indian and developed love, friendship, and mutual understanding beyond the racial barrier.

The next day I proposed to Henny and brought an engagement ring - ... The next day I took Henny to the ring. She never took it off her finger (Lives.370)

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Social and intellectual constructs that place males over women are known as patriarchy ([11]). According to Walby, women, children, and property, all fall under the control of males in a patriarchal society [12]. In a patriarchal society, male dominance, male leadership, and male power are encouraged. Economic dependency, domestication, and the marginalization of women are all part of this system. Because of this, some forms of the job are classified as "men's work" and others as "women's work" [13].

Patriarchal culture is characterized by gender inequity, misogyny, and male dominance, among other things [14]. Marriage and family have been particularly hard-hit by these qualities [15]. Patriarchy refers to a social structure in which power rests exclusively with the male head of the household. This implies that he is in charge of the family's assets and income and preferences for work, play, and family life in general [16]. On the other hand, different cultures place varying weights on these matters [17]. For example, in Arab and Palestinian civilizations, the patriarchal system is more significant in terms of the dominance of males over women (see [18-19]).

Those who live in patriarchal societies believe that men are inherently superior to women. Possibly, this is why Sultana [20] referred to patriarchy as the primary hindrance to women's growth and advancement. It is common for patriarchal theorists to overstate the biological distinctions between men and women, arguing that males are born with masculine, dominating, and superior roles. In contrast, women are born with subservient or feminine roles. One study found that "men can generally win the seeming assent of the same women they persecute" [20] because of this dominant mindset. Through numerous institutions, like academia, church, and the home, such males can achieve this by justifying and reinforcing female inferiority and subjugation to men. [21].

IV. CONCLUSION

As a result, Vikram Seth is a multi-genre author who does not confine his work to a single area or setting. "A writer about human people, not a salesman of Indian exotica," is how Namita Gokhale describes Vikram Seth, an international writer who is "deeply entrenched in his unique Indian identity, but a citizen of the world in the truest sense." (Cited in Multiple Locations, 34) – To us Indians, Vikram Seth's work may be regarded as a writer in any genre or setting. As a result, he might be considered a writer of Indian Writing in English. Regarding this topic, it is worth citing Anita De Sai's statement: "Seth belongs to the generation born after Independence who have drawn attention both in India and abroad, even making the pursuit of reading and producing books a legitimate hobby." (Sitting Pretty 26)

Vikram Seth has depicted the state of ladies in post-freedom India in this novel. His lady's characters are related to the family groups. Male heads of family, for example, Mr. Mahesh Kapoor and the Nawab of Baitar, commend the ideal residential space where people live inside the particular jobs designated to them.

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